

EXTENDED DATA

Title: Long-term outcomes after hip fracture in Ireland: a protocol for a systematic review of traditional and grey literature

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EXTENDED DATA 1. Full Search Strategy

Sources: MEDLINE (Ovid), Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, CINAHL, Conference Papers Index (Proquest), Rian, Dissertations and Theses: UK and Ireland (Proquest), DART Europe, Lenus, Department of Health, Health Service Executive, Health Information Quality Authority, Health Research Board, Irish Research Council, HRB Open Research, clinicaltrialsregister.eu and clinicaltrials.gov.

MEDLINE (Ovid)

1. exp Femoral Fractures/
2. ((hip or hips or cervical or femoral\$ or femur\$ or intracapsular or "intra capsular" or subcapital or "sub capital" or transcervical or "trans cervical" or basicervical or "basi cervical" or extracapsular or "extra capsular" or trochant\$ or subtrochant\$ or pertrochant\$ or intertrochant\$) adj5 (fracture\$ or break\$ or broke\$)).ti,ab,kf.
3. (((head or neck or proximal) adj5 (fracture\$ or break\$ or broke\$)) and (femoral\$ or femur\$)).ti,ab,kf.
4. or/1-3
5. (Ireland or Irish or Dublin or Cork or Limerick or Galway or Waterford or Sligo or Donegal or Louth or Wexford or Tallaght or Beaumont or Tullamore or Connolly or Drogheda or Letterkenny).af
6. 4 and 5
7. limit 6 to yr="2005 - 2021"

Embase

1. 'femur fracture'/exp OR 'hip fracture'/exp
2. ((hip OR hips OR cervical OR femoral* OR femur* OR intracapsular OR intra-capsular OR subcapital OR sub-capital OR transcervical OR trans-cervical OR basicervical OR basi-cervical OR extracapsular OR extra-capsular OR trochant* OR subtrochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant*) NEAR/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)):ab,kw,ti
3. (((head OR neck OR proximal) NEAR/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)):ab,kw,ti) AND (femoral*:ab,kw,ti OR femur*:ab,kw,ti)
4. or/1-3
5. Ireland OR Irish OR Dublin OR Cork OR Limerick OR Galway OR Waterford OR Sligo OR Donegal OR Louth OR Wexford OR Tallaght OR Beaumont OR Tullamore OR Connolly OR Drogheda OR Letterkenny
6. 4 AND 5
7. publication year 2005-2021
8. Limit to Embase NOT Medline

Web of Science

All indices selected

- # 1 TS=((hip or hips or cervical or femoral* or femur* or intracapsular or intracapsular or subcapital or subcapital or transcervical or transcervical or basicervical or basicervical or extracapsular or extracapsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*))
- # 2 TS=(((head or neck or proximal) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*)) and (femoral* or femur*))
- # 3 #2 OR #1
- #4 ALL=(Ireland or Irish or Dublin or Cork or Limerick or Galway or Waterford or Sligo or Donegal or Louth or Wexford or Tallaght or Beaumont or Tullamore or Connolly or Drogheda or Letterkenny)
- #5 #3 AND #4
- #6 #7 Timespan=2005-2021

CINAHL (Ebsco)

- S1 (MH "Femoral Fractures+") OR (MH "Hip Fractures+")
- S2 TX ((hip OR hips OR cervical or femoral* OR femur* or intracapsular or intra-capsular or subcapital or sub-capital or transcervical or trans-cervical or basicervical or basi-cervical or extracapsular or extra-capsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*))
- S3 TX ((head OR neck OR proximal) NEAR/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND TX (femoral OR femur*)
- S4 S1 OR S2 OR S3
- S5 TI AB SO AF GI PB ((Ireland or Irish or Dublin or Cork or Limerick or Galway or Waterford or Sligo or Donegal or Louth or Wexford or Tallaght or Beaumont or Tullamore or Connolly or Drogheda or Letterkenny))
- S6 S4 AND S5
- S7 S4 AND S5 - Limiters - Published Date: 20050101-20211231

Scopus

(TITLE-ABS-KEY (hip or hips or cervical or femoral* or femur* or intracapsular or "intra capsular" or subcapital or "sub capital" or transcervical or "trans cervical" or basicervical or "basi cervical" or extracapsular or "extra capsular" or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) W/5 fracture*) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY ((head OR neck OR proximal) W/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND (femoral OR femur*)) AND (AFFIL (ireland OR irish OR dublin OR cork OR limerick OR galway OR waterford OR sligo OR donegal OR louth OR wexford OR tallaght OR beaumont OR tullamore OR connolly OR drogheda OR letterkenny) OR CONFLOC (ireland OR irish OR dublin OR cork OR limerick OR galway OR waterford OR sligo OR donegal OR louth OR wexford OR tallaght OR beaumont OR tullamore OR connolly OR drogheda OR letterkenny) OR EDITOR (ireland OR irish OR dublin OR cork OR limerick OR galway OR waterford OR sligo OR donegal OR louth OR wexford OR tallaght OR beaumont OR tullamore OR connolly OR drogheda OR letterkenny) OR FUND-ALL (ireland OR irish OR dublin OR cork OR limerick OR galway OR waterford OR sligo OR donegal OR louth OR wexford OR tallaght OR beaumont OR tullamore OR connolly OR drogheda OR letterkenny) OR TITLE-ABS (ireland OR irish OR dublin OR cork OR limerick OR galway OR waterford OR sligo OR donegal OR louth OR wexford OR tallaght OR beaumont OR tullamore OR connolly OR drogheda OR letterkenny))

Limit to 2005-2021

ProQuest

Dissertations and Theses

1. noft(((head OR neck OR proximal) near/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND (femoral OR femur*))
2. noft((hip OR hips OR cervical OR femoral* OR femur* OR intracapsular OR intra-capsular OR subcapital OR sub-capital OR transcervical OR trans-cervical OR basicervical OR basi-cervical OR extracapsular OR extra-capsular OR trochant* OR subtrochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant*) NEAR/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*))
3. 1 OR 2
4. noft(Ireland or Irish or Dublin or Cork or Limerick or Galway or Waterford or Sligo or Donegal or Louth or Wexford or Tallaght or Beaumont or Tullamore or Connolly or Drogheda or Letterkenny)
5. 3 AND 4

Rian (Irish Repository)

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND (fracture))

in all fields for all item types. Limit to 2005 on.

Lensus (Irish Repository)

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND (fracture))

Department of Health Reports

Advanced Google Search:

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND fracture) site:gov.ie filetype:pdf

Health Service Executive Reports

Advanced Google Search:

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND fracture) site:hse.ie filetype:pdf

HIQA Reports

Advanced Google Search:

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND fracture) site:hiqa.ie filetype:pdf

Health Research Board Grants Awarded

Advanced Google Search:

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND fracture) site:hrb.ie

Irish Research Council Grants Awarded

<https://research.ie/awardees/>. Search "fracture"

HRB Open Research

Search: fracture

clinicaltrialsregister.eu

((hip OR femur OR femoral OR intertrochanteric OR subtrochanteric OR intracapsular OR subcapital OR transcervical OR basicervical OR extracapsular OR trochanteric OR pertrochanteric) AND fracture)
Select Country: Ireland

clinicaltrials.gov.

Condition or disease= fracture
Country= Ireland

EXTENDED DATA 2: Data Extraction Template

General information

Study ID:

Title:

Publication Year:

Publication Type:

Lead author and contact details:

Location of data collection (within Ireland):

Methods

Aim of study:

Study design:

Inclusion criteria:

Exclusion criteria:

Method of recruitment of participants:

Sampling method:

Sample size calculation described (yes/no/unclear)?

Participants

Number of patients eligible/ contacted:

Number of participants included:

Response rate by subgroup if described (Any information provided about those who were not included?):

Mean/ median age, SD/ IQR (Please specify):

Sex (% Female):

Fracture types (%):

Procedure types (%):

Outcome collection

Start date of data collection:

End date of data collection:

Setting of data collection:

Outcomes collected (post discharge or at fixed time-point after 30 days):

Method of data collection:

Proxy collection used?:

Criteria for proxy collection if applicable:

Training of data collectors in outcome collection described (yes/no/unclear)?:

Number and description of data collectors:

Same data collection methods for all participants (yes/no/unclear)?:

Outcomes

Specific outcomes collected: Number 1, 2, 3 etc

Outcome 1 definition:

Outcome 1 collection time-points:

Outcome 1 results: Report at each time point collected (for continuous outcomes: mean/ median, SD/IQR; for categorical outcomes: numerator, denominator, percentage estimates and 95% confidence intervals

Outcome 2 definition:

Outcome 2 collection time-points:

Outcome 2 results: Report at each time point collected (for continuous outcomes: mean/ median, SD/IQR; for categorical outcomes: numerator, denominator, percentage estimates and 95% confidence intervals

Outcome 3 definition:

Outcome 3 collection time-points:

Outcome 3 results: Report at each time point collected (for continuous outcomes: mean/ median, SD/IQR; for categorical outcomes: numerator, denominator, percentage estimates and 95% confidence intervals

Other outcomes definitions:

Other outcome collection time-points:

Other outcome results: Report at each time point collected (for continuous outcomes: mean/ median, SD/IQR; for categorical outcomes: numerator, denominator, percentage estimates and 95% confidence intervals